

SUMMARY.

1. The range of iodine value of different samples of butter fat is very wide (30-50) (Literature gives this as 25-47. Holde-Bleyberg, 7th edition, p. 802). (Katalenwasser-stoff öle and Fette.)

2. The linolic acid content of authenticated samples of butter fat is fairly constant and the range of variation comparatively very low (8.5-5.4).

3. One of the samples (No. 10) was found to contain no linolic acid and hence it is easy to conclude that the sample did not contain any butter-fat at all.

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Putrefactive Decomposition of Bengal Silk Cocoon.

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It is a well known fact that silk cocoon in presence of water undergoes decomposition very quickly and in the silk industry during the process of maceration of the cocoons in aqueous liquids for the removal of the yarn, very often a heavy odour of putrefaction is evolved, particularly if the temperature of the atmosphere is high. The products of such putrefaction have never been investigated by any one up to this time and although from the chemical point of view this would be quite interesting, yet the present investigation was undertaken from a slightly different standpoint. From a private communication from his friend Dr. V. N. Vyas of the King George's Medical College, Lucknow, the present author came to understand that the product of putrefaction of silk acted as a strong pressor substance for the heart, raising the blood pressure to a considerable extent. Apparently this must be due to the formation of some substances of great physiological activity during the process of putrefaction of silk cocoon and this was a sufficiently interesting field for research. Consequently the present investigation was undertaken with a view to elucidate the constitution of the compounds formed during the putrefaction.

PUTREFACTIVE DECOMPOSITION OF BENGAL SILK COCOON 459

A large supply of pierced silk cocoons was obtained through the courtesy of the Sericulture Department of the Government of Bengal, Berhampore. A preliminary examination of the cocoons revealed that they contained 25·6% of sericin, 70·4% of fibrin, 2·2% of moisture and about 2·0% of inorganic matter. The cocoons were coloured bright yellow and apparently contained a fairly large proportion of colouring matter in the form of carotin. Complete hydrolysis by hydrochloric acid and subsequent estimation of the amino acids by Fischer's ester method gave the following results, which can be compared with the result obtained by Abderhalden and Brahm (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 61, 256) by the hydrolysis of Bengal silk as given in the table below.

	From Bengal silk cocoon by the present author.	From Bengal silk by Abderhalden and Brahm.
Glycin	28·4%	30·5%
Alanin	22·85	20·0
Serine	5·75	1·8
Leucine	0·85	1·2
Aspartic acid	Traces	0·8
Glutamic acid	0·8	Traces
Phenylalanine	0·8	1·4
Proline	Traces	1·0
Tyrosine	12·8	10·0

From the above table it will be apparent that the really great difference between the two sets of results lies in the comparatively large proportion of serine obtained from the silk cocoon by the present author.

The cocoons on maceration with about 50 times their weight of water and incubation at 37° about a week, underwent extensive putrefaction and lost 35% of their weight during the process. The liquid expressed from the undecomposed fibres had a most nauseating odour, and on systematic working up as described in the experimental portion of the paper, yielded the following substances in the pure state in the form of their hydrochlorides: ammonia, methylamine, ethylamine, *p*-hydroxyphenylethylamine and aminoethanol (4·3%, 1·8%

5.8%, 2.1% and 0.3% respectively). Carbon dioxide was freely evolved during the process of putrefaction. From the afore-mentioned results it is quite apparent that the process of putrefaction of silk cocoon involved mainly two stages, namely, one of hydrolysis of the protein matter into amino acids and the other of elimination of carbon dioxide from the amino acids with the formation of amines, the two processes following each other so closely that at no time any great concentration of amino acids can be detected in the putrefying material. The amines mentioned above being well known pressor substances, particularly *p*-hydroxyphenylethylamine or tyramine, there is little wonder now that a decoction of putrefied silk cocoon would act as a strong pressor substance for the heart. The fibrous matter left after the putrefaction was over was found to undergo very little change on further treatment in the same way, and was practically pure fibrin. It had almost the lustre as ordinary silk fibre but only about half the strength. It was practically completely bleached after the putrefaction. It was not further examined chemically. It was also interesting to note here that the large proportion of ammonia evolved during the putrefaction must be due to the further degradation of the amines.

EXPERIMENTAL

100 G. of silk cocoons were macerated with 5 litres of distilled water and the mixture, contained in an wide mouth extraction flask, was incubated at 37° for 7 days. At the end of that period the light brown cloudy liquid with a disgusting odour of putrefaction was squeezed off from the fibrous material and filtered first through cloth and then through filter paper. The filtrate which had a strongly alkaline reaction was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness at first over free flame and finally on the water-bath. A dark brown slightly sticky, crystalline solid (yield 19.8%) was left behind and from a large number of experiments of the above type a total quantity of 268 g. of the solid was collected. This was refluxed with 3 litres of absolute alcohol and 30 g. of animal charcoal for nearly 12 hours and then filtered. The filtrate on cooling deposited a large amount of colourless crystalline needles which were filtered off, washed with absolute alcohol and dry ether and recrystallised from absolute alcohol. This product was termed *fraction A*.

The residue on the filter paper was extracted with boiling water, and the filtered extract evaporated to a small volume and allowed to

stand when a large amount of colourless feathery crystals separated out. These were filtered off and recrystallised from a small quantity of boiling water. This was termed *fraction B*.

The mother liquor from *fraction A* was evaporated to about 500 c.c. and allowed to stand in the refrigerator for 24 hours, when another crop of colourless needle shaped crystals separated out. They were filtered off and recrystallised from pure methyl alcohol in colourless hygroscopic needles. This portion was termed *fraction C*.

The mother liquor from the above was treated with dry petroleum ether until an oily precipitate was no longer formed. On allowing to stand in the refrigerator the oily product solidified and was filtered off and washed with dry petroleum ether. It was recrystallised from a mixture of equal volumes of dry petroleum ether and absolute alcohol in colourless prismatic needles. This was termed *fraction D*.

The mother liquor and the washings from the above were collected together and the whole evaporated to dryness. A pale brownish white, highly hygroscopic crystalline solid was left behind which was washed with small quantities of petroleum ether and finally recrystallised from a mixture of equal proportions of chloroform and benzene. The substance was thus obtained in pale cream coloured highly hygroscopic needles. This was termed *fraction E*.

Examination of the various Fractions.

Fraction A.—This melted at 269° and was easily soluble in water. On treatment of the aqueous solution with dilute caustic soda or ammonia an immediate white precipitate was formed which was filtered off and crystallised from xylene in colourless leaflets melting at 161° and identified to be *p*-hydroxyphenylethylamine or tyramine. The m. p. was unaltered on admixture with a genuine sample of tyramine obtained from Messrs. E. Merck. (Found: N, 10.61. Calc. for $C_8H_{11}ON$: N, 10.2 per cent).

Fraction B.—This did not melt at all but gradually sublimed on heating without leaving any residue. On treatment with caustic soda a strong smell of ammonia was evolved. The substance was identified as ammonium chloride.

Fraction C.—This melted at $223-24^{\circ}$ and crystallised in two forms, needles and leaflets. On treatment with dilute caustic soda no precipitate was formed, but a strong ammoniacal fishy odour was evolved. Aqueous solution of the substance gave an immediate preci-

pitrate with aqueous picric acid which on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 206° . The substance was identified to be methylamine hydrochloride and the m. p. was not depressed on admixture with a sample of the genuine substance obtained from Messers E. Merck. (Found: N, 20.9. Calc. for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$: N, 20.7 per cent).

Fraction D.—This melted at 73° - 78° and crystallised both in the form of prismatic needles and glistening leaflets. It was easily soluble in water and on treatment of the aqueous solution with dilute caustic soda no precipitate was formed, but a strong fishy odour was evolved. The aqueous solution gave immediate precipitates with dilute solutions of mercuric chloride, platinic chloride and chromic acid but not with aqueous picric acid. The crystalline substance on treatment with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave a crystalline acetyl derivative, m. p. 204° . The substance was identified to be ethylamine hydrochloride and was in all respects identical with a genuine sample of the substance prepared from Merck's 93% alcoholic ethylamine solution. The melting point was also not depressed on admixture with the prepared sample (Found: N, 17.6. Calc. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N H}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$: N, 17.1 per cent).

Fraction E.—This melted at 96° - 97° and was extremely hygroscopic. The aqueous solution was slightly acidic in reaction and gave immediate precipitates with aqueous platinic chloride and picric acid. The picrate crystallised from alcohol in large lemon-yellow hexagonal tablets melting at 158 - 59° . The substance was identified to be the hydrochloride of aminoethanol and on account of the highly hygroscopic character of the hydrochloride, the picrate was analysed. [Found: N, 19.0. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{NO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_3 \cdot \text{O}$ requires N, 19.3 per cent].

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